

INFLUENCE OF THE INTERFACE ON THE CREEP PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED MAGNESIUM ALLOY AS41

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SUMMARY: This paper deals with the investigation of creep properties of magnesium alloy AS41 reinforced by carbon short fibres. The specimens were produced by direct squeeze-casting. The short fibres showed planar isotropic distribution. The volume content of the fibres is about 16%. The investigation of the microstructure was carried out by optical microscopy and electron microscopy to characterise the interface and identify the precipitates at the interface. The creep tests were performed in a temperature range between 150°C and 300°C for a stress range of 30 MPa to 90 MPa. The results show the possibility of a reduction in the creep rate of the magnesium alloy AS41 by one or two orders of magnitude by introducing a reinforcing phase. The creep exponent determined using Norton-Baily-approach as calculated to lie between 5-7.

KEYWORDS: magnesium matrix composite, creep of MMC, magnesium alloy AS41, carbon fibres, creep exponent, activation energy for creep, interface strength

INTRODUCTION

There is a high demand for light metal matrix composites in automotive and aircraft applications. Light metal matrix composites (MMC) are already used for mass produced components or products e.g. partially reinforced aluminium pistons, crankcases and cylinder heads as well as particle reinforced brake disks [1,2]. A further reduction in weight can be achieved by replacing Al alloy matrix by magnesium alloys or by switching from ceramic fibres or particles to carbon fibres.

Magnesium alloys show poor creep properties due to their low melting point or low melting intermetallic phases. Efforts to improve the creep resistance have led to the development of magnesium alloys with Silver, Yttrium and rare earths (QE and WE series). These alloys are characterised by high melting point rare earth precipitates. Further improvement in the creep resistance is possible by reinforcement of these alloys with fibres.

The magnesium alloy AS41 (4wt% Al, 1wt% Si, 0.3wt% Mn, rem Mg) belongs to a group of magnesium alloys without rare earths as alloying elements, which show nevertheless acceptable creep properties for temperatures up to 150°C [3]. The aim of the reinforcement of this alloy was the extension of the application temperature up to 200°C and to reduce the creep rate in this temperature interval.

Several models have been proposed to explain the creep properties of short fibre reinforced MMC [4-10]. Some are based on continuum mechanics and others on microstructural or micromechanical models. The disadvantage of the micromechanical and microstructural models is its limitation to aligned short fibre MMCs. These models are not applicable to a planar isotropic fibre distribution. The continuum mechanical models enable the random planar distribution of the fibres to be considered but they cannot take into account other microstructural features. In this work these models were used to describe qualitatively the results. A quantitative description is not possible due to the number of parameters involved. Also these parameters cannot be reproduced for each series. The Norton-Baily-law (Eqn 1) was used to determine the creep exponent n and the activation energy Q_c for creep.

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{ss} = \alpha \cdot \sigma^n \cdot e^{\frac{-Q_c}{R \cdot T}} \quad (1)$$

ϵ_{ss} = secondary creep rate

α = constant

σ = applied stress

n = creep exponent

Q_c = activation energy for creep

R = gas constant

T = temperature

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The composite material was produced using direct squeeze casting technique [11]. A porous fibre preform was infiltrated by the molten alloy AS41 under a high pressure. The carbon fibre preforms showing a random planar fibre distribution with a SiO₂-binder were manufactured by Didier Werke AG, Wiesbaden, Germany. The carbon fibres had a diameter of 7 μ m and a mean length of about 150 μ m. The fibre volume fraction of 14-17% was determined by interrupted segment method on metallographic sections of the squeeze cast material. The preform was preheated up to 630°C in CO-atmosphere. The temperature of the melt was 800°C. Specimens were taken from the composite sheets parallel to the planar isotropic distribution of the fibres. Cylindrical creep specimens were produced with a gauge length of 25.4 mm (1"). Constant stress tensions creep tests were carried out in air at temperatures between 150°C and 300°C. Stresses between 30 MPa and 90 MPa were applied. The variation in temperature during the creep tests was ± 1 K. It took an average time of 2-3 hours for heating the specimens to test temperature before loading. Strain was measured using nimonic extensometers rigidly affixed to the specimen holders. The specimen displacement was measured by highly sensitive linear variable displacement transducers with a resolution of $8 \cdot 10^{-6}$ strain. The displacement values and the temperature were recorded simultaneously during creeping.

The electron microscopy investigations were carried out using a Hitachi X650 scanning electron microscope (SEM) and a Philips CM30 transmission electron microscope (TEM) with an acceleration voltage of 300kV. The TEM specimen were prepared by ion milling.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The micrographs in Fig. 2a and b show the difference between a reinforced and an unreinforced material. The unreinforced material shows the typical cast structure with

dendrites. Typical Mg_2Si precipitates (Chinese script) were also observed. This typical cast structure was also observed in the reinforced material. Due to the fibres a more globular structure was formed during the solidification in the squeeze cast process. The distribution of the fibres is not homogenous. Fibre agglomeration and unreinforced areas were observed. An good performed interface without any pore is shown in Fig. 3. Some precipitates in the interface can be observed. Most of them can be identified as Mg_2Si .

Fig. 2: Microstructure of unreinforced AS41(a) and a carbon fibre reinforced AS41 (b)

Fig. 3: SEM-micrograph of the interface C-fibre/AS41

One aim of the reinforcement of light metals is the improvement of the creep properties i.e. a general reduction of the creep rate and at the same time increase of the temperatures of application. Fig. 4 shows typical creep curves for two applied stresses for reinforced and unreinforced AS41 at 200°C. The creep curves for the unreinforced as well as for reinforced AS41 show the typical three stages of creep. The MMCs behave differently compared to unreinforced materials. In the primary creep stage the load transfer to the fibres takes place. This leads to an extension of primary creep region which is about 1/3 of the creep time to rupture. This is followed by a shortened steady state creep region where this region takes 1/2 of the creep time.

This phenomenon is typical for short fibre reinforced material because the creep mechanisms in reinforced materials differ from those in monolithic metals [9,10]. Dlouhy et al. have stated that primary creep in short fibre reinforced material is dominated by load transfer from the matrix to the fibres due to a work hardening zone at the interface fibre - matrix [9]. This model was developed for aligned fibres. It is not surprising that the time for primary creep is increased significantly due to the random planar fibre distribution. During creep the fibres are not only carrying the load, they are also obstacles for dislocations. Tertiary creep takes most of the time. It is controlled by recovery processes and by fibre breakage. Only a few fibres in some creep specimen were broken but it has to be determined whether the reason is the creep process.

Fig. 4: Comparison of typical creep curves of unreinforced and carbon short fibre reinforced AS41 at 200°C

The behaviour described of the reinforced material is strongly dependent on the testing parameters such as temperature and load. The length of the various creep stages is quite different. For example a creep test at 150°C and 50 MPa shows a primary creep for over 2 months and no secondary or tertiary creep because only work hardening mechanism operates.

In all cases the creep properties of the reinforced metal are much better than the properties of the unreinforced metal. The secondary creep rates of the reinforced materials are more than one order of magnitude lower than those of the unreinforced material. The time to fracture increases also about one order of magnitude.

The values measured of the secondary creep rate for reinforced AS41 are listed in Table 1 and plotted in Fig. 5. The values in Table 1 are mean values of the measured creep rates. The creep exponent n was determined by linear regression. As shown in Fig. 5 only a few measurements to determine the creep exponent n . Nevertheless the points deviate in most cases not very much from the regression line. Hence the experimental results can be qualitatively understood but for a detailed interpretation more work is necessary.

Table 1: Minimal creep rates of carbon short fibres reinforced AS41

	150°C	200°C	225°C	250°C	275°C	300°C	Q
30MPa	-	-	$3.8 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{s}^{-1}$	$8.5 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{s}^{-1}$	-	$1.9 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{s}^{-1}$	144kJ
40MPa	-	$1.3 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{s}^{-1}$	$1.9 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{s}^{-1}$	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{s}^{-1}$	$7.7 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{s}^{-1}$	-	178kJ
50MPa	-	$4.1 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{s}^{-1}$	$5.2 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{s}^{-1}$	$3.1 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{s}^{-1}$	-	-	172kJ
60MPa	$5.9 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{s}^{-1}$	$1.8 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{s}^{-1}$	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{s}^{-1}$	-	-	-	136kJ
70MPa	$1.2 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{s}^{-1}$	$3.8 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{s}^{-1}$	-	-	-	-	-
80MPa	$2.6 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{s}^{-1}$	-	-	-	-	-	-
90MPa	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{s}^{-1}$	-	-	-	-	-	-
n	4.2/13.8	6.4	5.3	6.7	n.d.	n.d.	-

In the temperature range between 200°C and 250°C the values of the creep exponent lie between 5.3 and 6.7. The regression line indicates that the assumption of a power law creep mechanism is correct and also the value of the creep exponent is in the range of the power law creep ($n=3-8$). At 150°C a change in the creep exponent was observed. At stresses between 60MPa and 80MPa the creep exponent is 4.2 and for stresses between 80MPa and 90MPa the creep exponent increases up to 13.8. This may be explained by the high loads (power law breakdown). The tensile yield strength of AS41 is about 90MPa at 150°C. If it is assumed that after load transfer to the fibres the matrix has to bear lower stresses, the stresses in the matrix are less than the yield strength. At high stresses recovery processes are more dominant and this may lead to a breakdown of the interface.

At 200°C the creep exponent of the unreinforced AS41 was 7.7 and is thus greater than that for the reinforced AS41. This behaviour is unusual, but may be explained as follows. A temperature of 200°C is for an unreinforced AS41 a high temperature ($0.7 \cdot T_E$) and several thermally controlled processes are possible. Creep depends strongly on diffusion. As the load in reinforced material is transferred from the matrix to the fibre the matrix carries a lower load and this should have an influence on the creep rate.

The activation energy calculated for creep is given in Table 1. Values between 140kJ/mol and 180kJ/mol were found. These values are higher than the activation energy of self diffusion of magnesium. Thus it can be assumed that the mechanism for creep does not depend on the

creep properties of the matrix. Dlouhy et al. [9] have pointed out that the rate controlled processes for creep in short fibre reinforced metals operate in the workhardening zone (WHZ) surrounding the fibres. Therefore the activation energy depends on the properties of the WHZ.

Fig. 5: $\log \varepsilon$ - $\log \sigma$ diagram for reinforced AS41: determination of the creep exponent n

The interface in fibre reinforced metals is very important for the composite properties. Hence the behaviour of the composite depends on the characterisation of the interface. It is well known that wetting of carbon fibres by pure liquid magnesium is very difficult. Nevertheless the high pressure during squeeze casting overcomes this problem. There is only a short time during the casting process for reactions between fibre and matrix to take place. For this reason reaction products such as carbides are not expected. Fig. 3 and Fig. 6 show good bonding between fibre and matrix. The interface is dense and no pores are observed. A small dense layer (0.5 -1.5 μm) of precipitates and some isolated precipitates are visible around the fibres. An analysis of this layer provides the evidence of magnesium, aluminium and silicon. A particular phase could not be identified. The major precipitate which could be identified in the matrix as well as at the interface is the intermetallic phase Mg_2Si . This phase occurs in different forms. In the matrix the typical chinese script form was observed. There are also big blocky precipitates of Mg_2Si (Fig. 8). These precipitates result from a reaction of magnesium and silicon. It is assumed that the silicon comes mainly from the reaction of the SiO_2 -binder of the preform with the liquid or solid magnesium. A reaction between magnesium and SiO_2 leads to Mg_2Si and MgO . The selected area diffraction pattern in Fig. 7 shows rings of weak intensity of a polycrystalline phase. Only very fine distributed particles at the interface matrix precipitates could be the reason for these rings. An analysis of the pattern indicates that these rings could come from MgO , but it is not clear yet. In Fig. 6 other precipitates occur. The EDX-analysis indicated an increased Manganese and Aluminium concentration but an identification of the phase was not possible. Due to these precipitates a high interface strength between the fibres and the matrix can be assumed. Hence it can be considered that the

interface is the reason for the improvement of the creep properties. Further improvement of creep properties can be expected from higher fibre volume fractions.

Fig. 6: TEM micrograph of a carbon fibre reinforced AS41 alloy showing a random orientation and some coarse precipitates

Fig. 7: TEM bright field image of a typical coarse Mg₂Si precipitate

Fig. 8: Mg₂Si situated at a carbon fibre

CONCLUSION

The creep properties of carbon short fibers reinforced magnesium alloy AS41 were investigated. A pronounced improvement of the creep properties for the reinforced alloy in comparison to the unreinforced alloy was observed, although the distribution of the fibres was not homogenous. The analysis of the creep tests using the Norton-Baily approach shows that the creep exponent varies from 5 to 6.5 in the temperature range from 200°C to 250°C. At 150°C a transition of the creep exponent from 4.2 for low stresses to 13.8 for high stresses up to the yield strength was observed. Activation energies were calculated in the range from 140kJ/mol to 180kJ/mol.

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